

A Musicological Approach to Data Sonification in Real-Time Immersive Systems

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I declare that this dissertation is all my own work, except as indicated in the text.

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Abstract

By turning data into sound, sonification provides access to structures and dynamics that may remain hidden to the eye, enriching analysis of large datasets, communication, and even accessibility solutions. Yet, when it comes to the most fundamental form of transmitting information through sound—speech — there is a striking lack of sonification studies framed within the rules and structures of linguistics. While much research has addressed mappings based on pitch, timbre, or rhythm, very few have systematically explored sonification as a process governed by phonetic, syntactic, and semantic constraints— that is, the very principles underlying the transmission of knowledge.

This study frames sonification as a musicolinguistic “Conceptual Structure” (phonetic + syntactic + semantic) and evaluates it comparatively inside a real-time *E. coli* simulation. Although tested here within a Biology based simulation, the framework may be considered domain-agnostic, and its principles potentially can be directly extended to other fields where complex, dynamic data demand perceptual access — ranging from cosmology and astrophysics to environmental monitoring and human–computer systems. This study is an attempt to move the concept of sonification beyond being regarded solely as the production of technical sound signals or solely as an aesthetic compositional practice.

In a Unity-based, eight-zone environment, the audio synthesis chain is held constant while only the mapping logic varies. Five scenes are implemented: Genomic parameters Optimal Temperature, Optimal pH, UV Resistance, and Toxin Resistance were mapped onto: J (Phonetic) — formant-based vowel synthesis; K (Semantic) — “alien score” → tonal cadence (PAC → ... → DC); L (Syntactic) — mod12 tetrachord → melody; M (Hybrid/Conceptual Structure) — simultaneous binding of layers; N (silent control). The experiment design is within-subjects; every participant experiences all scenes. Measures include immersion (IEQ-SF), mental workload (NASA-TLX), an EEG-derived attention index (non-overlapping 5-s windows, participant-specific z-scoring), plus preference and brief free-text responses. All states are written to a unified JSON log; EEG uses a veto policy and a 30-s personal baseline. Sample size: $n = 10$.

The sonified–silent immersion contrast (H1a) is not statistically significant; however, RM-ANOVA reveals a scene effect, with Hybrid (M) exceeding Phonetic (J) and Syntactic (L) on immersion. No between-scene differences are found for NASA-TLX; EEG attention likewise shows no significant differences. Preference is dominated by Hybrid (M, 80%), with J and L at 10% each. Accordingly, H1a is not supported; H2a receives partial support ($M > J, L$ on immersion); H2b–H2c are not supported; H2d is failed to be rejected under current sample. Given the small sample and short EEG windows, workload and EEG results are interpreted as exploratory.

(i) A real-time test environment that compares phonetic/syntactic/semantic sonification mappings under a fixed audio synthesis chain; (ii) an empirical indication that Conceptual Structure increases immersion; (iii) a reproducible design template (layer separation and rebinding, single-dimension variance control, unified logging).

Statistical power is limited ($n = 10$). Future studies should employ larger samples, higher-channel EEG, cross-cultural semantic mappings, and enriching the conceptual structure components layer-wise.

Keywords: data sonification; auditory interface; human–centred design; musicolinguistics; real-time data–sound mapping.

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1. Introduction

Sound has long been used as a medium for transferring knowledge, from the earliest human rituals to the highly technologised environments of contemporary science. In most of these contexts, the focus remained either on music proper or on practical sonic signals such as alarms and speech. Today, the word sonification has been systematically employed to describe such transmission of information, especially in scientific practice. Yet, the idea that sound can carry and structure information is older than the terminology, and is deeply related to how humans experience and organise the world in time. Sound is dynamic; it unfolds; it allows the encoding of relations otherwise invisible. For this reason, it is safe to state that sonification is not only a means of communication but also an organised perception protocol.

In the present study, sonification is approached through a musico-linguistic lens. According to NASA's definition, sonification is “the transmission of information through sound” [1]. Many studies in the field arrive to “somehow musical” results; but there exists an older and perfectly fitting instrument that also transmits information through sound: language. There is no natural law that forces language to be only consisted of words; the linguistic approach can be applied to other rule-governed sonic systems, including music and sonification. Works that set natural, rule-based correspondences between music and linguistics indicate such a common basis [2], [3]. In short, both natural language (word-based) and music language (melodic-structural) are organised temporal forms carved by the same intellectual capacities, visible through different grammars.

Historically, the Chess analogy echoed by the linguist Karl Kraus and later tensioned by composer and music theorist Anton Webern pointed that “applying the rules” and “following the rules” are not identical conditions; a language may be spoken or a piece may be composed without strictly enumerating all rules, yet some grammar still operates underneath. Yet, one has to apply and follow the rules of the game if they want to play Chess [4]. In this context, Webern's suggestion is that the type of rules in linguistic and music are similar [4]. Antović's Musicolinguistics frame this intuition more systematically: music has phonological, syntactic, and semantic levels; perception is central; and cross-mapping is legitimate and productive for theory [5]. Bierwisch's equation — Phonetic Form + Logical Form (Syntax) + Semantic Form = Grammar = Conceptual Structures = Conceptual Knowledge — gives a compact way to express how surface signals and conceptual knowledge interlock [6]. This paper adopts that equation as a scaffolding for sonification: phonetic, syntactic, and semantic layers are not rhetorical metaphors but operational layers for mapping data into sound.

From this stance, sonification should not be confined to the aesthetic sequencing of tones, as if it were nothing more than creative composition. It becomes a protocol for producing conceptual knowledge via sound, if its layers are designed coherently and evaluated empirically.

Under phonetics, vowel-like timbres are known to be represented in auditory cortex along formant spaces; synthetic vowels elicit systematic responses [7]. This suggests a phonetic route for robust timbre mapping.

Syntactic regularities in music —generally intervallic relations, chordal structures [3], ordered pitch-class sets [8]— provide an abstract but analysable medium to encode multivariate data, independent of tonality.

Temporal features and tonal-harmonic context act as an interpretive layer, have been thought as the equivalent to Semantic Form in language; identical surface chords can have different functions depending on context [6], [9], [10].

Although phonetic, syntactic, and semantic layers of music are considered as above in this study, they are not necessarily limited to those elements of music. These selections are justified and their alternatives are discussed in the following sections.

This study focuses on perceptual-experiential outcomes of the applied sonification methods: immersion/engagement (achieved via IEQ-SF) [11], mental workload (achieved via NASA-TLX) [12], momentary concentration (achieved via EEG-derived index), and user preference (achieved via custom survey —see appendices—). Additionally, an immersion-based manipulation check (again IEQ-SF) is used as control, because comparing a silent control with any sound condition should, by design, produce strong differences.

Methodologically, a within-subjects design is adopted: all participants experience all five scenarios (J: Phonetic, K: Semantic, L: Syntactic, M: Conceptual Structure (Hybrid), N: No-sonification control). The audio synthesis chain remains constant (oscillators, shaper, filters, limiter, modulator index), while the mapping logic is what varies in between experimental conditions. The experimental loop is simple and transparent: baseline, scenario run, short survey; EEG windows are artefact-checked and z-scored against personal baseline during the recoring. The order of scenarios is counter-balanced. In this sense, the study tries to balance ecological validity (real-time, playable system) with statistical clarity (controlled pipeline, repeated measures). These topics will be covered in detail in the Methodology and Analysis sections.

A linear regression model which is introduced in detail in the following sections, trained on example genomic inputs and synthesiser outputs, implements these mappings. The system integrates real-time interaction, visual feedback, and structured data logging to ensure reproducibility.

The simulation models an eight-zone cubic environment populated by evolving *E. coli* agents. Their behaviour is driven by genome-encoded traits under changing environmental conditions. Four genomic parameters — optimal temperature, optimal pH, UV resistance, and toxin resistance — of the currently selected cell are continuously sonified. The system combines real-time interaction, visual feedback, and structured data logging to ensure reproducibility.

Beyond practical evaluation, a conceptual point is also tested: when phonetic timbre, syntactic order, and semantic context are bound together (conceptual structure), does the system produce a more coherent and useful experience? The expectation, following the musico-linguistic argument, is that binding across layers may increase immersion and perceived traceability without necessarily increasing workload. This expectation remains modest on EEG, as concentration measures in short windows can be noisy; nevertheless, they are reported to see tendencies and for future modelling.

In short, the present hypotheses discussed in this paper argue that sonification can be framed as Conceptual Structure in the Bierwisch sense: phonetic + syntactic + semantic layers operating together to map data into sound in a way that is formally structured, perceptually grounded, and conceptually meaningful. The contributions are intended to be both empirical and methodological:

- A unified comparative testbed where phonetic, syntactic, semantic, and Hybrid mappings are implemented under a constant synthesis chain and evaluated in real time.
- An empirical assessment of immersion, workload, concentration, and user preference across mappings, including a principled manipulation check.
- A practical design template for real-time mixed-reality sonification that can be replicated or extended, such as alternative cadence systems; multi-voice spectral mappings.

2. Mapping and Research Question

In this section, the mapping of sonification approaches used in the study is explained and the research questions are clarified. The main motivation is to see how different musicological levels (phonetic, syntactic, semantic) when used alone or together to create a conceptual structure (hybrid approach) are affecting participants' experiences. Mapping strategies are defined in a way that they are consistent with previous literature but also answering the needs of the experimental design.

2.1 Sonification approaches

phonetic approach (J)

Genomic parameters (optimal temperature, pH, UV and toxin resistance) are mapped directly on vowel formants (F1–F2–F3) via the trained linear regression model. The result is formant-based synthetic vowels. So at the phonetic level different timbres are generated and became distinguishable for the participant.

semantic approach (K)

From genomic data, “alien score” metrics are calculated and matched with tonal classical cadences. More adapted situations are represented by Perfect Authentic Cadence (PAC), while more unfit situations are represented by Deceptive Cadence (DC). The linear regression model maps the alien score to the genomic parameters. Full list of cadence presets contains Perfect Authentic cadence as well as Plagal Cadence, Imperfect Authentic Cadence, Half Cadence and Deceptive Cadences. The functional-semiotic power of cadences are used, expressing the concept of biological adaptation through musical meaning.

syntactic approach (L)

Typically by using the linear regression model, genomic data are transformed to note frequencies according to mod12 principle, creating tetrachords. These tetrachords are transformed to melodic lines and played continuously by the Audio Synthesiser. The purpose here is to make the genetic variables audible inside a melodic organisation.

conceptual structure (hybrid) approach (M)

Phonetic, syntactic and semantic levels are working at the same time. Formant-based vowels (phonetic), melodic structures (syntactic) and tonal cadences (semantic) are produced simultaneously and completed each other. This Hybrid approach represents the Conceptual Structure in literature model and is the main focus of the experiment.

2.2 Hypotheses

H1 (Manipulation Check): Tests whether the sonified scenes (J, K, L, M) are clearly distinguishable from the silent control scene (N). The aim is to confirm that the manipulation is perceptually registered by participants:

H1a. Tests whether the sonified scenes produce higher immersion scores than the silent scene.

Note: Mental workload, concentration, and preference are not included in this control check; they are evaluated under the main hypotheses. The manipulation check only verifies whether the presence of sound is perceptually registered, which is most directly reflected in immersion scores.

H2 (Main Hypotheses — Evaluation of the Hybrid approach): Tests whether the Hybrid (M) approach has stronger effects compared with the Phonetic (J), Semantic (K), and Syntactic (L) approaches:

H2a. Tests whether the hybrid approach produces higher immersion scores.

H2b. Tests whether the hybrid approach produces higher concentration scores.

H2c. Tests whether the hybrid approach produces lower mental workload.

H2d. Tests whether the hybrid approach is most frequently preferred by participants.

3. Literature Review

In this chapter first the literature about sonification is reviewed. The focus is kept on two main directions: (i) theoretical discussions about the relation between music and language at phonetic, syntactic and semantic levels, and (ii) biological data sonification and the technical side of the question “how to sonify”. First, the tool and synthesis side is introduced, works that directly explain the mapping of data to sound in the low-level or timbre domain. After that, the theoretical frameworks are discussed, where music and language are compared as formal systems and possible correspondences are highlighted.

Second, the specific gap of this research is described. In the literature, there is no direct “Conceptual Structure sonification”. Yet, there are theoretical bases that suggest it [5]. By combining musico-phonetic, musico-syntactic and musico-semantic levels into one framework, this study extends the musico-linguistic theory into real-time sonification. So the review both gives background and also prepares the ground for why four approaches (J/K/L/M) were selected and tested in the experiment.

Sonification literature is very wide and heterogeneous. Applications range from astrophysical data sonification to medical signals (EEG, heart rhythms), also environment and image sonification. This variety shows that the method is not tied to one discipline, but considered as a tool for information transfer and perceptual discovery in many contexts. However, the parts that directly relate to this study are two: theoretical discussions about music–language relation, and biological data sonification.

3.1. Literature of Musico-Linguistic approaches

music - language interface and theoretical foundations

Antović’s “Musicolinguistics” framework argues that music, just like language, has a grammar with phonological, syntactic, and semantic levels [5]. Bierwisch’s equation “Phonetic Form + Logical Form (Syntax) + Semantic Form = Grammar = Conceptual Structures = Conceptual Knowledge” provides a theoretical basis for thinking sound structures as multi-layered conceptual systems [6]. Katz’s “Identity Thesis” points to formal processing similarities in language and music, suggesting not surface analogy but structural correspondences [3]. This theoretical direction allows sonification to be read not as only aesthetic sequencing, but as a protocol producing conceptual knowledge.

phonetic approach

Phoneme is defined as the smallest unit of speech in linguistics that differentiates a word or a linguistic element from another [17]. Especially vocal phonemes (vowels) are directly associated with the shaping of the mouth cavity and their consequent formant structures [18]. Therefore, analyses at a phonetic level depend on both articulatory and perceptual processes.

Oganian, Bhaya-Grossman, Johnson, and Chang suggested that representations for vowels, especially during listening, are not localised as a singular “/a/ neuron”, but instead organised as irregular neural populations that cover the formant space [7]. It was found that this representation to be normalised according to the speaker-subject, and defined on the two-dimensional formant coordinates and also applies to synthetic sounds as well as to natural sounds. This finding indicates that vocal phonemes have a neural representation in the human brain in spite of being synthetic. Therefore, it is safe to state that neural representations of the phonemes are not limited to linguistic inputs, but can also be triggered through sound synthesis.

Vocal phonemes —vowels— are traditionally classified on tongue height, tongue frontedness, and lip roundedness [19]. This triple classification shows that phonemic differences are set on physical acoustic-articulation bases.

IPA vowel chart demonstrates three basic articulation dimensions: tongue height (vertical axis), tongue frontedness (depth axis) and lip roundedness – left-right pairs. Thus, vowels are put on the chart by International Phonetic Association, according to the tongue placement and lip shape [20] (see Fig.1).

Ladefoged & Johnson argues that vocal phonemes can be articulated in different pitches — one can sing different notes with the same vowel; however, the main distinction is through two characteristic resonances – the Formants. The first formant is the one with the lower pitch (which you can hear in a creaky voice), and the second formant is the one with the higher pitch (which you can hear when you whisper) [18]. According to this, F2 roughly reflects the tongue frontedness - backness difference, while F1 reflects the features inversely related to height. In the other hand, Serrurier & Neuschaefer-Rube proposes a more detailed articulatory mapping: It suggests that F1 is related to tongue height, F2 to tongue frontedness – including lip roundedness effect, and F3 to lip roundedness – to a lesser extent to tongue height/frontedness [21]. These relations make systematic mapping of acoustic signals to the 3-Dimensional data space possible.

Phonetic features, within the context of non-vocal music, are directly a matter of instrumentation/orchestration (instrument family, material, articulations, amplitude envelope, and instrument/composition techniques). In other words, timbral differences at the same instrument or ensemble can be identified as divergence on phonetic level as well.

Vowel Space Chart

Figure 1. Vowel spaces and systems [18]

Importantly, superior temporal gyrus (STG) reacting to synthetic vowels [7] shows hope that formants can be transformed into a directly useable sonification method within sound synthesis-based systems. This situation indicates that real-time audio-visual interfaces may be built with linguistic inputs of synthetic vocals, and based on parametric computational acoustic simulations. In practice, — if formant frequency shift which is related to age and gender conception also taken into account (but not necessarily) — addressed together with F1-F2-F3, defines a four-dimensional audio feature space for data sonification.

syntactic approach

The term comes from Greek syntaxis — syn “together” + taxis “arrangement” — and it sits in the same family as symphony, synonym, synthesis; on the taxis side, think taxonomy and tactics. (Cf. symphony, synonym, synthesis; taxonomy, tactics) [22]. This etymology encodes the function relied on syntax — it is literally the act of putting things together in an arrangement, in other words, it is linear organisation.

Language is defined as a form-meaning interface and conceptualised mostly upon the transformation function of non-sequential thoughts to linear sequence —and vice versa. Consequently, syntax can be considered as a cognitive mechanism that helps the linear processing of cognitive representations [23]. In other words, syntax can be considered as a perceptual-cognitive tool that enables the organisation of thought into structured, sequential forms.

Neuro-scientific findings have proved that syntactic structures are supported by perceptual representations related to hierarchical parsing, especially in the posterior temporal gyrus (pMTG) region in the brain [23]. This observation shows that linguistic processes involve a critical hierarchical organisation in in perception-representation level.

A similar approach of this functional classification is also applies for music. The syntax of the music is defined by the structural relations between signs; horizontal and vertical intervalic relations, tonal/atonal connections, regulative elements such as sequence and contrast are building blocks of the

syntax [2]. Vertical sets create chords or spectra, while linear sets create melodies in time. These structures are parallel with the arguments on musical perception having an organisation similar to a systematic grammar.

Within the post-tonal theory in music, melodic and harmonic structures are expressed by pitch classes (PC). Here, frequencies are normalised by Arithmetic Modulo 12 (mod12), and every pitch belongs to one of 12 pitch class; +12 cycle defining an octave (e.g., $E\flat(3) + 12 = 15 \equiv 3$) [8]. This representation provides an abstract form, independent from tonal references. For example, given the reference $C = 0$, the sequence of — [10, 1, 2, 5] ($B\flat, D\flat, D, F$) — creates a tetrachord —a set of four notes— (See Figures 2,3, and 4).

Pitch-Class Integer Content

Integer Name	Pitch-Class Content
0	$B\#, C, D\flat$
1	$C\#, D\flat$
2	$C\#, D, E\flat$
3	$D\#, E\flat$
4	$D\#, E, F\flat$
5	$E\#, F, G\flat$
6	$F\#, G\flat$
7	$F\#, G, A\flat$
8	$G\#, A\flat$
9	$G\#, A, B\flat$
10	$A\#, B\flat$
11	$A\#, B, C\flat$

Pitch-Class Clockface

Figure 2. Pitch-class integer notation system [8].

Figure 3. Pitch-class clockface. [8].

Clockface Normal Form

Figure 4. Pitch-class integer notation system clockface [8]

This approach provides a methodological advantage in terms of data sonification: a data array with minimum of 3 and maximum of 12 dimensions – in equal temperament – can be created. To create a melodic line, there must be at least a Trichord (a set of three notes). Therefore, every dimension can be transformed into a format that is both compatible with structural music theory, and directly processable into computational models.

semantic approach

Semantics is defined as the philosophical/scientific research of meaning in natural/artificial languages [24]. Semantic Form (SF), is the interface between language and the conceptual knowledge in the brain. Gradation is formalised as a specific subfield of this interface, while Logical Form (LF) creates Syntactic relations, SF maps them to Conceptual Structures (CS) to create Conceptual Knowledge [6]. This mechanism is seen in the field of sonic art and scientific sonification tools as well.

Musical semantics is two-dimensional: intra-musical (e.g., tonal functions, cadences, pattern and textural repetitions) and extra-musical (e.g., anthem = national identity, lament = evoking death,) [2]. Additionally, in some cases it can be a temporal cue such as the “horn call” [25]. This differentiation is important because a musical element can have both a structural function, and a cultural or associative meaning. Sonification practices are fed on extra-musical sources by its nature; that is, sonification already carries a “visualisation” or “representation” function out of music. However, if one looks at data sonification through a research or interactional lens, the use of intra-musical semantics framework may be more useful. The reason for this is that structural elements provide a systematically analysable and regular semantic framework.

Katz & Pesetsky suggests a critical conceptual expansion at this point: the Tonal-Harmonic Component (THC) operates as an interpretive plane independent from musical syntax, and corresponds to SF in linguistics [6]. For example, the same A-minor chord can carry a completely different scale-degree function according to context; thus it is safe to state that the relations around its tonal environment define its musical meaning in harmonic and temporal context. This is the main assumption of the Roman numeral analysis and shows that the “meaning” in music arises from contextual relations.

Schlenker, on the other hand, argues that musical meaning derives from two sources: from general auditory cognition processes (e.g., perceptive dimensions such as loudness, temporality, timing), and specific formal features of the tonal space (structural relations such as dissonance, cadence, modulation) [26]. This dual perspective requires considering both the perceptive-psychological dimension, and the theoretical-structural dimension within musical semantics research. In other words, the perception of a chord as “loud” or “slow” from the audience is as much a part of the semantic analysis as which tonal axis the chord exists.

One or multiple aforementioned musical features can be used as a semantic approach for data sonification purposes. This approach provides a medium to sonify the datasets in various dimensions according to which semantic musical features are used. In the following sections, a detailed Musico-Semantic based sonification mapping example will be evaluated.

conceptual structure (hybrid) approach

First, this approach is built on the typical “Phonetic Form + Logical Form (Syntax) + Semantic Form = Grammar = Conceptual Structures = Conceptual Knowledge” principle [6]. The main idea is that these three layers that create the essential essences of language can be adapted one-to-one to musical or sonic structures, and can create a meaningful sonification grammar. In other words, data sonification can be thought as not necessarily only the random or aesthetic sequence of sounds, but also a system that produces conceptual knowledge by joining linguistic layers together.

Second, the hybrid perspective also highlights that these levels interact with each other. For instance, the syntactic arrangement of a melodic line may directly shape the semantic features it evokes, while the phonetic features (such as timbre, register, or envelope) can influence the perception of the

structural role of the same line. In this sense, the Conceptual Structure works as a “binding mechanism” that connects the different sonification layers into a coherent whole.

This approach facilitates the design of different sonification grammars according to the creativity of the developer or the artist, the context of the project, and the targeted experience. For example, even a 4-voice chord progression created from vocal phonemes in the most basic form (phonetic level) – that is, a specific cadence type (semantic level) – can create a sonification grammar that is understandable and consistent within itself, with the melodic lines naturally deriving from this progression (syntactic level).

Therefore, the Hybrid model should not be considered as a “mixture” of the syntactic and semantic approaches. It is a higher-level framework where multiple representational layers converge. This framework, by integrating phonetic, syntactic, and semantic domains, ensures that the outcome of sonification can be evaluated as a systematic grammar that forms conceptual knowledge from data, instead of aesthetic sequences.

In summary, phonetic, syntactic and semantic layers have been studied both in linguistics and in music, and their potential for systematic mapping has been established [3], [5], [6]. Bierwisch’s formulation provides the theoretical background that these levels are not independent, they are interrelated within a higher-order framework. In this study, this formulation is extended into the domain of sonification. While there is no direct precedent for a “Conceptual Structure sonification” in the literature, the current design operationalises this theoretical principle by combining phonetic (formant-based vowels), syntactic (tetrachord melodies) and semantic (cadences) layers into a single hybrid approach. In other words, the model is not taken directly from previous sonification research; it was derived from musicolinguistic theory and adapted here as a new framework for real-time data sonification.

3.2. Tools and Synthesis Contributions

Grond, Bovermann and Hermann proposed a SuperCollider vowel synthesis class, bringing phonetic level parameters directly into sound synthesis [13]. These kinds of work focus on the “how to sonify” problem and strengthen the low-level (phonetic/timbre) mapping layer, yet, they do not offer a linguistic or musical theoretical framework.

3.3. Biological Data Driven Applications

Braun, Tfirm and Ford showed that sonification can support discovery in biological research [14]. Minciacchi & Rosenboom’s edited volume collects interdisciplinary examples of perceptualising biological information [15]. In visual domain, Toffa & Mignotte follow a semantic mapping logic, transforming images into literal sounds (e.g., dog→barking) [14]. This research employs semantic means in sonification methodology, yet, it does not construct a linguistic based conceptual structure.

3.4. Gap and Position of This Study

Existing literature gives, on one side, tool/synthesis and application works [13], [14], [15], [16], and on the other side, theoretical frameworks about language–music relations [2], [3], [4]. But studies that test phonetic, syntactic and semantic layers in a musical lens in the same experimental architecture, comparative and real-time are still rare. This study brings these two lines together, by implementing a musico-linguistic approach in an *E. coli* simulation with four strategies (phonetic, syntactic, semantic, Hybrid) and a control condition. In all scenarios, the synthesis chain is kept constant, only the independent variable (e.g. formant / f0 derived control / Chord-Melody / Cadence type) is changed, so that effects of methods can be observed without side variables. In this way, the theoretical claims in literature are tested in an applied and measurable framework.

4. Methodology

This section is written to explain why and how the methods were used, and to keep the flow of the experiment clear for the reader. First, the simulation architecture with optimisation and basic usability was introduced. Then, the fixed audio synthesis chain and the use of USB MIDI controller (Novation Launch Controller XL) are described. After that, the Linear Regression model is presented in short theory and its implementation inside the Unity project. Later, the four sonification strategies as case-studies (phonetic, syntactic, semantic, hybrid) are explained one by one. EEG data collection and the logging pipeline are also summarised, so the dataset is reliable and analysable. Finally, participant information, ethics, and the experimental procedure are given, so design–implementation–measurement are connected as one complete framework.

4.1. Reproducible HCI Experiment Setup

Methodologically, testing inside a real time evolutionary simulation was considered appropriate, since sonification methods studied in this experiment work linearly. For this reason, a Unity-6 based *Escherichia coli* simulation system model was developed into a transparent 3D cube mesh divided into eight zones. Each zone was populated; mutation and phage-based horizontal gene transfer were enabled; to keep measurement stable, four features were focused on: optimal temperature, optimal pH, UV resistance, toxin resistance. With a Novation Launch Control XL, temperature, pH, UV, and toxin of each zone were changed on the fly, and the effects on division and adaptation were observed. The genomic stream was mapped to sound by a Linear Regression model with low latency, and the synthesiser was driven continuously; in this way biological dynamics could be both seen and heard.

Technically, the audio chain (*oscillators* → *waveshaper* → *EQ/filters* → *limiter*) was kept constant across scenes, while only the mapping dimension was changed (formants, modulo-12 tetrachord, cadence class, or their Hybrid) depending on the experiment condition. EEG was recorded in 5-second windows, artefact-checked, z-scored against a 30-second personal baseline for the beginning of each experiment condition, and mapped to a 0–100 “concentration” index. All states (baseline readiness, vetoes, scores) and all survey answers were written into a unified JSON log (SPSS-friendly) for traceability. Participants provided short demographics, completed a tutorial, and then experienced all five scenes in counter-balanced order; after each scene, IEQ-SF and NASA-TLX plus one free-word response were completed. Ethically, withdrawal was possible at any time and data could be deleted by username.

4.2. Simulation Architecture, Optimisation and Usability

In this section, the simulation structure, optimisation process, and usability are explained in detail. The purpose is to make the experiment setup transparent in terms of data recording, user interaction, biological modelling, and the sonification outputs. First, the architecture of the simulation and behavioural parameters of *E. Coli* agents are introduced. Then, evolutionary dynamics, observation and logging logic are presented. Finally, user interface and the experiment flow are introduced.

The simulation consists of eight isolated, transparent, cube-shaped water-tank prefab; each zone was assigned with a number and a colour to make sure they are observable. This is achieved by a slow orbital camera movement around the cube. Each zone is initially populated with 1000 nutrition prefabs; once this number is reduced to half, the stock is automatically refilled to 1000.

E. Coli cell prefabs were created with respect to a genome structure based on a ScriptableObject. This genome carries information of movement habits (chemotaxis), metabolic cost and energy, environmental adaptation, resistance parameters, and social behaviours. The actions of the cells are informed by sensory processes and “punishments” caused by environmental incompatibilities.

If the energy level is lower than the defined threshold, the agents gets into a dormancy state. Reproducing was controlled with a threshold modulated by age and population density.

Figure 5. Simulation Interface, where yellow objects are nutrient prefabs and red dots are phage prefabs

Evolutionary dynamics were modelled through mutational variations and horizontal gene transfer. Mutation rates were defined by a fixed multiplier for each individual genomic parameter. The horizontal gene transfer done with conjugation with neighbouring agents and phages.

The Python based EEG measurements were received using User Datagram Protocol (UDP). When recording was active, written under the session sections of a JSON file. Python-based streaming processes could be launched or terminated directly from within Unity; control messages provided graceful shutdown. The “ESC” key was assigned first to stop EEG recording, and then to terminate the experiment.

Figure 6. EEG Python UDP Bridge

In terms of experiment flow, participant demographics (user name, country of origin, exposure to Western classical music) was collected through Unity UI panels and stored inside the JSON file both in flat (SPSS-compatible) and text-based (human readable) formats. The Experiment Menu provided access to Tutorial and Sonification J/K/L/M/N scenes for each user. At the end of the experiment,

participants were asked to report their preferred sonification style; this information was saved into the preferences section of the JSON file. A Rest Lobby scene provided a break with a countdown timer; once the timer reached zero, the selected scene was automatically started. Warnings were displayed for missing usernames or misconfigured build scenes if any exists.

Overall, the system combined an environment simulation model with eight ecological zones, genome-driven agent dynamics, horizontal gene transfer (phages) and mutations, together with 3D real-time visualisation. Nutrient resources were spatially modelled by means of a three-dimensional diffusion grid. When consumption fell below half of the initial level, stocks were automatically replenished.

The genome logger highlighted one cell every seven seconds as the “selected cell” with a bright blue emission material. This visibility remained throughout the selection duration (in this experiment typically seven seconds). The rest of the cells remained semi-transparent. In this way, the user was clearly shown which cell was driving the sonification at that moment. In parallel, the environmental zone parameters were displayed dynamically as an array at the top right corner of the screen; continuous feedback was provided on temperature, pH, UV and toxin values. On the left, the interface displayed the genome values of the selected cell, its generation number, its corresponding zone, and population-level metrics including total population and total births. Thus, the attributes of the cell interacting with the system were made both audible and directly observable.

Figure 7. Simulation “Selected Cell” Zoomed-In

Support from a large language model, ChatGPT 4o, was used only for code generation and debugging in C# during the simulation development in Unity. Prompts such as “*Write a C# script named CellHighlighter.cs. Whichever cell is currently logged should have its material changed from its own material to a material I will specify, for the duration of logging. When a new cell is logged, the previous one should revert to its original material, and the newly logged cell should adopt the specified material.*” and “*The tumble behaviour of my cells depends on measured nutrient density in the environment of the cell. Update this behaviour in code so, it can also be manipulated by a noise value I define, adjustable in the inspector.*” were used.

4.3. Initial Conditions

At the start of every experimental scene, all eight zones are initialised to the same baseline: temperature 20 °C, pH 7 (neutral), UV index 0.01, and toxin index 0.01. These environmental parameters remain under participant control throughout each run.

The spawned colonies are seeded with genomes aligned to this baseline: `optimalTemperature = 20`, `optimalPH = 7`, `uvResistance = 0.01`, and `toxinResistance = 0.01`. This yields complete environmental

matching at $t=0$ in all conditions (AlienScore ≈ 0 in the semantic and hybrid conditions), ensuring that subsequent dynamics arise from user manipulations, stochastic variation, mutation, and horizontal gene transfer rather than from initial mismatch.

4.4. MIDI Controller Interface

In this experiment, Novation Launch Control XL MIDI controller has been used for user control of the simulation environment. The device contains 8 columns, each representing a different defined isolated cube shaped zone in the main environment. Within each column on the controller, four main environmental parameters of the zone can be directly adjusted:

- Toxin level (0–2) is controlled through the first row of rotary knobs.
- pH (0–14) is controlled through the second row of rotary knobs.
- UV Light index (0–2) is controlled through the third row of rotary knobs.
- Temperature (0–100 °C) is controlled through the fader at the bottom of the column.

Figure 8. Novation LaunchControlXL simulation environment interface representation (Dall-E generated by showing the photograph of the controller)

With this structure, the user is able to modify environmental conditions of each zone in real time, and by creating different combinations, directly influence the sonification outputs of the experiment. The reminder tags were written on paper tapes and posted on the body of the Novation MIDI controller, for sustaining usability. Also, the users were able to see and hide the controller buttons page by pressing the “C” button on the keyboard. The current parameter values manipulated by the user were monitored on the right-upper corner of the screen.

4.5. The Linear Regression Model

The model used in this study is based on the linear regression model developed inside Unity-Real Time Machine Learning Tool Kit [27].

In the context of Unity-RTML ToolKit, linear regression is optimised to work in real-time. The training process and the prediction stage can be done directly inside Unity Inspector. User sets the parameters `inputSize`, `outputSize` and `modelType` and adds the model into the scene. During the process, data is recorded, in the “train” step the coefficients are learned, and in the “run” step the model starts to produce real-time predictions. Trained models can be saved in JSON format and reused in different sessions.

The main reason of using linear regression in the experiment is the low latency it provides for real-time interaction. RTML-ToolKit test results show that the model is very lightweight and fast, with average 2 milliseconds training time and less than 1 millisecond prediction time. This performance is critical especially for processing the biological data produced continuously by the simulation (i.e. optimal temperature, pH, UV resistance, toxin resistance) and mapping them instantly to the sound synthesiser.

The application logic in the experiment works as follows: first, genomic parameters generated by the Unity-based *E. coli* evolutionary simulation are taken as inputs of the model. The linear regression model weights these multidimensional inputs with its coefficients and generates continuous outputs. These outputs are then mapped into the sound synthesiser, thus creating a direct bridge between biological data and musical parameters. In this way, the dynamics of biological processes can be followed both in visual and auditory plane in real-time.

This approach provides two main contributions in the context of sonification: (i) establishing a relation between data and sound that is statistically explainable and repeatable, (ii) creating an experimental environment open to user interaction thanks to the real-time functioning of the simulation and the sonification models.

4.6. The Audio Synthesiser

In this study, the audio-synthesiser script (`Synth.cs`) is constructed as a typical and conventional chain including two oscillators (with additive wavetable), an modulation algorithm (`Add`), a wave shaping unit (`fuzz`), and a multi-band linear filtering (3-band parametric EQ + 4-band frequency filters: Low-Pass / High-Pass / Band-Pass). The wavetable is generated with 16 harmonics across 2048 samples and normalised; oscillator mixer (sine, square, saw, triangle, ramp, wavetable) is energy-balanced to prevent unpleasant peaks and clippings.

Within the experimental design, only the independent variable specific to each scenario —e.g., formant frequencies — has been changed. All other synth parameters are kept constant across conditions. Thus, as mentioned before, the synthesis chain runs always with the same “fixed” configuration; only the assigned independent variable (such as formant centres or f_0) is updated between scenarios. This constraint keeps structural/timbral consistency of auditory stimuli, projects the variance into a single dimension, and minimises unwanted side-effects (gain fluctuation, dynamic difference, spectral spreading) inside the processing pipeline.

4.7. Methodology of Musicolinguistic approaches

phonetic

On the basis of source-filter framework, a harmonically rich periodic source wave has been used in the main audio oscillator and then filter with the formants— F_1 - F_2 - F_3 . Due to the pulse shape of the source stimulation has been shown to significantly affect perceived vowel quality [28], [29], a sawtooth-like stimulation has been preferred in practice and formant targets have been adjusted accordingly. The F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 frequency values used in the training process of the linear regression model to generate the vocal phonemes synthesised and used in this study are shown in the table below. Due to the linear nature of the defined genomic parameters during the sonification, unique vocal phonemes not defined in the table can also be synthesised and heard during the simulation.

Table 1. Some Vocal Phonemes Formant Frequencies (Training Data)

Vocal Phoneme	≈ F1 (Hz)	≈ F2 (Hz)	≈ F3 (Hz)
/ju:/ as in “music”	679	1125	2578
/i:/ as in “keep”	303	2080	2907
/ʊ/ as in “good”	391	982	2617
/u/ as in “goose” in Californian dialect	417	1434	2479
/ɜ:/ as in “term”	481	1428	2321
/ɒ/ as in “hot” in British Dialect	485	876	2719
/e/ as in “best”	474	1861	2614
/ɑ:/ as in “car”	679	1125	2578

Table compiled from [18] and [44].

Genomic data – Optimal Temperature, Optimal pH, UV/Toxin Resistance – are classified in binary form by normalising the minimum and maximum intervals defined in the simulation. Based on this classification, *E. coli* genomic combinations have been calculated to train the Linear Regression model as seen in the table below:

Table 2. *E. coli* Agent Genomic Classes of the simulation (Training Data) (binary form)

Genomic Combination	Optimal Temperature (0-100°C)	Optimal pH (0-14)	UV/Toxin Resistance (0-1)
1	High	High	High
2	High	High	Low
3	High	Low	High
4	High	Low	Low
5	Low	High	High
6	Low	Low	High
7	Low	High	Low
8	Low	Low	Low

As aforementioned, vocal phonemes can be categorised according on three characteristics: roundedness, frontedness, and height.t [21]. For the phonetic sonification of the data, a matched mapping has been created as in Table 2 and Table 3, using this classification:

Table 3. Vocal Phonemes Classified

Vocal Phoneme	Tongue-Height	Tongue-Frontedness	Lip-Roundedness
/ju:/ as in “music”	High	High	High
/i:/ as in “keep”	High	High	Low
/ʊ/ as in “good”	High	Low	High
/u:/ as in “goose” in Californian dialect	High	Low	Low
/ɜ:/ as in “term”	Low	High	High
/ɒ/ as in “hot” in British Dialect	Low	Low	High
/e/ as in “best”	Low	High	Low
/ɑ:/ as in “car”	Low	Low	Low

Table compiled from [18].

At first look, these tables appear to be correlated regarding dimension and order. However, it is essential to recognise their complex interrelation, as F1 pertains to tongue height, F2 to tongue frontedness—including the effect of lip-roundedness—and F3 to lip-roundedness, with a lesser association to lip height and frontedness. [21]. Also, some of the relations are direct, some are inversely proportional [19]. That means each element of the two sets is not only affecting/being affected by just one element. They have a dependent interrelation as multiple elements in the other set. Linear Regression model was founded useful to overcome this challenge, as it learns in weighted arrays.

Four Linear Regression Model—a model for each pitch index—was used in the scene. The models have been trained to have genomic input/output for every situation, and saved to be used in the scene. Therefore, a unique phoneme has been created for each linear and unique genomic data combination.

In the simulation, genomic data read from a randomly selected cell in a different environmental zone every 7 seconds is processed by linear regression model in real time and the synthesised vocal phoneme is heard for 2 seconds over the 7-second period repetitively, and then cut off. This management is done by a Note Looper object. At the end of the 7-second period, another cell is randomly selected in a different environmental zone and the same process is repeated during the scene. Synthesiser envelope parameters have been set to Attack = 10 ms, Decay = 50 ms, Sustain = 60%, and Release = 50 ms. The genomic data of the selected cell is printed on the screen near the 3D water tank, simultaneously with the sonification.

syntactic

In the syntactic sonification approach, as in the other scenarios, the genomic parameters of optimal temperature, optimal pH, UV resistance, and toxin resistance were used. A Melody Looper object was created to control the Audio Synthesiser. The Melody Looper generates melodic output by applying an amplitude envelope with Attack = 10 ms, Decay = 50 ms, Sustain = 60%, and Release = 50 ms. Functionally, it receives a tetrachord input — for example [0, 4, 5, 11] —, maps it to note frequencies through Mod 12, and assigns them sequentially to the frequency parameter of the synthesiser’s main oscillator. The melodic line is looped continuously, with a 0.01-second pause between successive notes and a 1-second rest between melodic blocks. The mapping between the note entries and the genomic parameter as follows:

- Note 1 (Mod12) → Optimal Temp (Mod12)
- Note 2 (Mod12) → Optimal pH (Mod12)
- Note 3 (Mod12) → UV Resistance (Mod12)
- Note 4 (Mod12) → Toxin Resistance (Mod12)

The dynamic data obtained from the Genome Logger were normalised to a range between 0 and 12 (corresponding to an octave). For each genomic parameter, the minimum was mapped to 0 and the maximum to 12. For instance, in the case of temperature, the environmental minimum of 0 °C and maximum of 100 °C were mapped to a 0–12 range. The Linear Regression model took each genomic parameter as input and transformed it into a pitch-class set element that formed part of a tetrachord which was then sent to the Melody Looper object to be played as a melody in time.

In this scenario, no phonetic variation was introduced between notes; each note retained the same timbral quality. The sound was produced through frequency modulation synthesis: a sawtooth wave audio oscillator was modulated by a sine wave audio oscillator with a modulation index of 2.01, yielding a typical synthesiser tone.

Within the simulation, as in other conditions, every 7 seconds a “selected cell” was chosen and logged by the Genome Logger. In this scenario, the cell was sonified using the syntactic method described above, producing a continuous melodic output. The genomic data of the selected cell again is printed on the screen near the 3D water tank, simultaneously with the sonification.

semantic

In this experiment, classical cadences were used as the semantic musicolinguistic tool. Cadences are hierarchically arranged according to the level of tension they convey and resolve. The classic cadence taxonomy, ordered from lowest to highest tension, is as follows:

- Perfect Authentic Cadence (PAC): $V \rightarrow I$; essential structural closure [10].
- Plagal Cadence (PC): $IV \rightarrow I$; typical of sacred music; “Amen” cliché [30].
- Imperfect Authentic Cadence (IAC): $V \rightarrow I$; weakened authentic effect [10].
- Half Cadence (HC): $x \rightarrow V$; remains on the dominant; can serve as harmonic interruption before recapitulation [10].
- Deceptive Cadence (DC): $V \rightarrow vi/VI$; often used to be “corrected” by PAC later in Sonata-Allegro form [10].

This ranking provides a one-dimensional linear axis for semantic sonification. A set of four audio oscillators controlled by a Chord Controller game object were placed in the scene, and the oscillators used the same wave format and synthesis parameters described in the Syntactic Sonification scene. The linear regression model provided a one-dimensional continuous output in the range $[0, N]$, where N is the number of cadence presets (five in this experiment). According to this value, the output was mapped directly to one of the cadence presets in the Chord Controller object. Each preset consisted of a fixed chord progression that culminated in one of the five cadences listed above. Chord Controller basically takes four predefined tetrachords which are in melodic form, and plays them simultaneously as four parts as soprano, tenor, alto and bass, and ends a cadence of two chords connected to the chord prolongation. To reinforce the temporal (time-related) semantic effect, the final two chords which create the cadence last three times longer than the others. The outcome is a chord progression ends with a cadence.

The “Alien Score” was used as the controlling input variable for this semantic mapping. It was determined by comparing the optimal genomic parameter values of the selected *E. coli* cell (temperature, pH, ultraviolet radiation, and toxin resistance) with the actual environmental conditions in its location. For each dimension, the absolute difference between the optimal and real value was normalised by the corresponding tolerance parameter, clamped to [0,1], and averaged across all four dimensions. A value of 0 thus represented full environmental adaptation, while 1 indicated maximum incompatibility. In practice, lower Alien Scores were mapped to PAC (maximum adaptation), while higher Alien Scores were mapped towards DC (minimum adaptation).

Alien score is calculated pragmatically in this study as follows:

$$Dev_i = \frac{|x_{actual} - x_{ideal}|}{Tolerance_i}, \text{ where } x \text{ is genomic parameter.}$$

$$Dev_i = \min(1, Dev_i), \text{ normalising between 0 and 1.}$$

$$AlienScore = \frac{Dev_{temp} + Dev_{pH} + Dev_{UV} + Dev_{toxin}}{4}$$

As with the phonetic sonification, genomic data were sampled from a randomly selected cell located in a different environmental zone every 7 seconds. These data were processed in real time by the regression model and mapped to one of the cadence presets. Simultaneously, the environmental and genomic values of the selected cell were printed on the screen near the 3D water tank, ensuring that the sonification could be directly compared with the visual representation. With respect to this logic, the selected cell is sonified and the user were exposed to cadences mapped to the genomic data they can monitor on the screen.

conceptual structure (hybrid)

In this experiment condition, the phonetic and semantic approaches were combined —the syntactic features naturally occurs through the melodic lines. A Chord Controller and a Note Looper object were placed in the scene. One Linear Regression Model (LRM) was trained to predict the phonetic output, while a second one was trained to map genomic data to a cadence preset index.

The Note Looper component generated vowel features based on the phonetic mapping typically as in the phonetic experiment condition, following the formant-derived vowel synthesis model described earlier. At the same time, the Chord Controller produced harmonic progressions culminating in cadences determined by the Alien Score, as explained in the semantic approach.

The Hybrid scenario therefore allowed the sonic output to operate on multiple levels: at the phonetic level, distinct vowel-like timbres were heard; at the syntactic level, the Note Looper naturally occurring melodic patterns from chord progressions; and at the semantic level, these patterns were placed within harmonic contexts defined by cadential closure. Together, these outputs formed a Conceptual Structure that integrated sound in terms of timbre, melodic organisation, and harmonic meaning.

As in the other scenarios, a cell was randomly selected from one of the environmental zones every seven seconds, and its genomic values were logged and processed in real time. Each selected cell triggered both phonetic and semantic sonification streams simultaneously. The synthesiser envelope

parameters (Attack = 10 ms, Decay = 50 ms, Sustain = 60%, Release = 50 ms) were kept constant, ensuring comparability across conditions. The genomic and environmental values of the selected cell were displayed on screen beside the simulation tank, providing the participants with a multimodal correspondence between visual data and Hybrid sonification.

4.8. EEG Data Collection

EEG data were acquired with a 4-channel BrainBit headset over local BLE and processed via BrainFlow [31]. Prior to the main measurement, a 30-second personal baseline was collected, segmented into non-overlapping 5 s windows. Each window was processed channel-wise through a denoising pipeline (de-trend → 250 Hz notch (BrainBit default) → 1–45 Hz band-pass → wavelet denoise), after which spectral band powers (δ , θ , α , β , γ) were estimated. From these, the principal metric was computed as $\text{raw} = \frac{\beta}{\alpha + \theta}$. Baseline statistics were then derived for raw, γ , and total power (mean and standard deviation; in cases of limited clean windows, median and MAD were used as robust estimates). These baseline values established the reference distributions for subsequent z-scoring.

During the experimental phase, data were continuously buffered and consumed as strictly non-overlapping 5-second windows to ensure that no segment was reused. Each window was subjected to an artefact veto policy: γ and total power were normalised against their baseline distributions, and if the resulting z-scores exceeded configurable thresholds (lenient or strict mode, with limits on consecutive vetoes), the window was discarded. For valid windows, the raw ratio was z-scored against the baseline $z = \frac{\text{raw} - \mu_{\text{raw}}}{\sigma_{\text{raw}}}$, mapped through a logistic function (gain ≈ 1.2), and scaled to a 0–100 “concentration” score. Each window was further labelled (“High focus”, “Neutral”, or “Low focus”) according to its z-score range.

All states—including baseline progress and readiness, veto rejections, and concentration scores—were transmitted to Unity as UDP JSON packets. Inside the Unity, when recording was enabled, the EEGMetricsUdpReceiver component appended samples into a unified UserData.json file under the active user–scene–session node, with periodic flushing (once per second) to ensure data persistence. Control of the system was designed for simplicity for the researcher: R toggled recording, K/J toggled overlay visibility, and the Python streamer responsible for BrainBit interfacing could be launched or stopped directly from Unity. A separate UDP control channel was reserved for graceful termination, where Unity sent {"cmd": "shutdown"} before process exit.

With this methodology, the collected EEG data was de-noised, artefact-checked, normalised against a 30 seconds individual baseline, and recorded in a structured way, providing easily analysable concentration scores across experimental conditions.

4.9. Experiment Conditions (5 scenarios)

1. Phonetic approach
2. Semantics approach
3. Syntactic approach
4. Conceptual Structure (Hybrid) approach
5. No sonification (control)

Technically, a real-time AudioSynthesiser code was written, and a Linear Regression model was implemented for Genome to Audio mapping. Every scenario was given to ten people, and at the end of each scenario a survey was asked. During the scenarios, attention and concentration levels were measured with EEG headset using BrainFlow library in Python. At the start of each scenario, 30

seconds baseline data was collected, de-noise functions of the library were applied, and too noisy data were vetoed. In the surveys, NASA-TLX and IEQ-SF were included.

All scenarios were coded with simple tags, named Sonification J, K, L, M and N, so that participants could not know which letter represents which method to prevent bias. In phonetic approach, four genome inputs were pushed into F1–F2–F3 formant values, and different vowels were synthesised. This mapping was not manual, it was done through linear regression model, so that vowel change is coming directly from data. In syntactic approach the same four genome inputs were mapped onto the four digits of a tetrachord as frequencies, and a melody line was generated for each sequence. In semantic approach, from the same four environmental inputs an “alien score” was calculated, and this score was then connected to cadences in tonal music. PAC was considered the most adapted, DC the most unfit. According to the expectation and meaning functions of cadences in music, PAC was mapped to zero and DC to highest values. Again, the linear regression model was used for this. In this way phonetic, syntactic and semantic layers are parallel and working in the same modelling logic.

The original instrument of IEQ-SF comprises three factors: Involvement, Real-world dissociation, and Challenge. Because the present design is an observational simulation rather than a goal-directed game, participants do not encounter performance outcomes such as “winning,” “losing,” or “mission success.” Accordingly, the three Challenge items (original items 9–11) were removed from the survey to prevent confusion within participants. The adapted form thus contains eight questions, covering only Involvement and Real-world dissociation. Such context-specific adaptation is common in psychometrics and is used to preserve content validity by aligning item content with the task ecology. The exact wording and item mapping of the adapted IEQ-SF are provided in the appendices.

The flow of the whole experiment was: first demographics, then short explanation about the simulation and nature of *E. coli* bacteria, then a tutorial scene, after that a two minute demo, and then the test part. Each scenario itself was eight minutes of play, two minutes of survey (NASA-TLX, IEQ-SF, plus audibility survey) and two minutes of rest. The order of scenarios was counter-balanced between participants.

From ethical side, every participant had the right to withdraw at any moment and delete their data if they wish. At the very beginning they had to choose a username, which could later be used to remove their data anonymously. At the very end of experiment, participants were asked which scene they would prefer if they had to use a sonification tool in the future.

- Flow: demographics (including choosing a username) → brief information on simulation and the nature of the *E. coli* bacteria → tutorial scene → 2 min demo → test.
- Every scenario: 8 min game → 2 min survey (NASA-TLX, IEQ-SF, plus custom mini-survey) → 2 min rest. At the end, condition preference was asked to each participant.
- Order of the scenarios were distributed counter-balanced.
- Ethically, all participants have a right to withdraw and delete their data in any given moment.
- They have chosen a username at the beginning; this can be used to delete data anonymously if they desire.
- At the very end of the experiment, participants were also asked about their preference of scene in case they would need to use a sonification tool.
- Data collected were kept in a secure hard-drive until uploaded to university OneDrive service once secure internet connection was established.

4.10. Participants

Table 4. Participant Profiles

Username	Region of Origin	Western Classical Music Exposure (1-5)	Condition Order
ALIEN	Asia	2	N, K, L, M, J
BEAL	Asia	3	K, J, N, L, M
COCO	Asia	3	M, L, J, K, N
ENNNY	Africa	4	J, K, L, N, M
EYLA	Africa	5	N, L, K, M, J
HP	Europe	4	M, K, L, N, J
KD	Africa	3	L, M, N, K, J
P10	Americas	4	N, J, L, K, M
THECUTFATHER	Europe	5	L, K, N, M, J
TONY	Europe	5	K, L, J, N, M

4.11. Ethics

The study received approval from the project supervisor on June 2025 and conducted in the following three-months. All procedures conformed to institutional and international guidelines for human-subjects research.

Adult volunteers (≥ 18 year-old) without any known neurological or severe hearing conditions were eligible.

Participants read an information sheet and provided written informed consent before any procedure. Withdrawal was permitted at any time without penalty, and data could be deleted on request via the assigned username.

The protocol was non-invasive. EEG was recorded with a consumer-grade, 4-channel device in accordance with manufacturer guidance and the participants were informed that was not a medical test. Audio levels were kept within safe listening ranges; breaks were scheduled between scenes; no deception was employed. Adverse-event reporting procedures were in place, though none occurred.

Personal identifier data were not collected; usernames served as pseudonyms. Session logs and survey responses were stored on an encrypted local drive and subsequently transferred to a secured institutional OneDrive once secure connection was established. Access was restricted to authorised research personnel. Raw data will be destroyed after presentation.

A brief debriefing summarised the study aims and provided contact information for queries or data deletion.

Data analyses were conducted with IBM SPSS Statistics version 31 under the institution's licensed software, and the simulation was developed using Unity 6 student license provided by the University of Nottingham.

5. Results and Analysis

5.1 IEQ-SL

Immersion (IEQ-SF) scores were examined between the control scene (N) and sonified scenes (J: Phonetic, K: Semantic, L: Syntactic, M: Hybrid). Descriptively, the control condition yielded $M = 2.68$, whereas the average across sonified scenes was $M = 3.23$ (Table 5.1). A paired t-test did not

reach significance, $t(9) = 1.74$, $p = .116$, Cohen's $d = 0.55$, 95% CI [-0.13, 1.21], indicating a medium-sized, yet non-significant effect. By contrast, a repeated-measures ANOVA showed a significant scene effect, $F(3,27) = 3.77$, $p = .012$, partial $\eta^2 = .295$ (large effect). Pairwise comparisons indicated Hybrid (M) significantly exceeded Phonetic (J) ($p = .006$) and Syntactic (L) ($p = .018$); the difference from Semantic (K) was not significant ($p = .108$).

H1a was not supported (sonified vs. silent immersion difference not statistically significant); however, the medium effect size suggests a tendency in the expected direction. Partial support emerged for H2a ($M > J$ and L on immersion). The expected sonified–silent gap under H1a did not appear; this does not invalidate the manipulation, yet, indicates that tighter measurement or increased statistical power may be required.

Table 5.1. Scene-wise IEQ-SF means

Scene	M	SD	n	95% CI [LL, UL]
J (Phonetic)	2.76	0.61	10	[2.33, 3.20]
K (Semantic)	3.30	0.41	10	[3.01, 3.59]
L (Syntactic)	3.14	0.67	10	[2.66, 3.62]
M (Hybrid)	3.74	0.59	10	[3.32, 4.16]
N (Control)	2.68	0.84	10	[2.07, 3.28]

5.2 NASA-TLX

Descriptively, sonified scenes $M = 9.92$, control $M = 8.85$. The paired t-test was not significant ($t(9) = 0.97$, $p = .357$, $d \approx 0.31$). RM-ANOVA met sphericity (Mauchly $p = .645$) and showed a borderline main effect ($F(3,27) = 2.97$, $p = .050$, partial $\eta^2 \approx .248$). Bonferroni-corrected pairwise tests revealed no differences (M – J : $p = .141$; M – K : $p = 1.000$; M – L : $p = .230$). Result: H2c was not supported; Hybrid did not reduce workload.

Table 5.2. Scene-wise NASA-TLX scores

Scene	M	SD	n	95% CI [LL, UL]
J (Phonetic)	10.42	2.27	10	[9.14, 12.39]
K (Semantic)	9.03	1.67	10	[7.84, 10.23]
L (Syntactic)	8.85	3.47	10	[6.37, 11.33]
M (Hybrid)	9.92	1.96	10	[8.59, 11.25]
N (Control)	8.85	2.19	10	[7.27, 10.43]

5.3 EEG Concentration

Scene means were $J = 41.0$, $K = 40.9$, $L = 46.2$, $M = 44.0$, $N = 50.4$. Shapiro–Wilk rejected normality for all ($p < .001$); a Friedman test was therefore applied and was non-significant ($\chi^2(4) = 2.00$, $p = .736$). Mean ranks were highest for N (3.50) and lowest for M (2.60). Result: H2b was not supported; no EEG concentration difference across scenes.

Table 5.3 Scene-wise EEG concentration scores

Scene	M	SD	n	95% CI [LL, UL]	Shapiro–Wilk p
J (Phonetic)	41.00	21.37	572	[39.24, 42.75]	< .001
K (Semantic)	40.86	26.72	594	[38.70, 43.01]	< .001
L (Syntactic)	46.23	26.52	538	[43.99, 48.48]	< .001
M (Hybrid)	44.00	27.06	572	[41.78, 46.23]	< .001
N (Control)	50.42	29.39	382	[47.47, 53.38]	< .001

5.4 Country of Origin

Preferences by region were: Africa 67% M / 33% J; Americas 100% M; Asia 100% M; Europe 67% M / 33% N (Table 5.5). The chi-square test was not significant ($\chi^2(6) = 5.00, p = .544$), with small cell counts noted. Descriptively, Hybrid was dominant across regions.

Table 5.4. Country × Preference distribution

Region	J (Phonetic)	K (Semantic)	L (Syntactic)	M (Hybrid)	N (Control)	Total
Africa	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (67%)	0 (0%)	3
Americas	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	2
Asia	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	2
Europe	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (67%)	1 (33%)	3
Total	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (80%)	1 (10%)	10

5.5 Western Classical Music (WCM) Exposure

ANOVA was not significant ($F(2,7) = 2.10, p = .193, \eta^2 \approx .38$); Kruskal–Wallis was likewise non-significant ($H(2) = 3.60, p = .165$). Descriptively, those preferring Hybrid (M) averaged 3.5/5 exposure; the two participants preferring J or N reported 5/5. Given the small sample, over-interpretation is avoided.

Table 5.5. WCM experience by preference group

Preference Group	n	Mean WCM Exposure (1–5)	SD
J (Phonetic)	1	5.0	–
L (Syntactic)	0	–	–
M (Hybrid)	8	3.5	1.2*
N (Control)	1	5.0	–
K (Semantic)	0	–	–

5.6 Preferences

Hybrid (M) was chosen by 80% of participants; Phonetic (J) and Syntactic (L) were each chosen by 10%; Semantic (K) and Control (N) were not chosen (Table 5.7). A goodness-of-fit chi-square was significant ($\chi^2(2) = 9.80, p = .007$), indicating a non-uniform distribution with Hybrid as the dominant choice. H2d was failed to be rejected under current sample.

Table 5.6. Sonification method preferences

Preference	Frequency	%
J (Phonetic)	1	10%
K (Semantic)	0	0%
L (Syntactic)	1	10%
M (Hybrid)	8	80%
N (Control)	0	0%
Total	10	100%

5.7. General Assessment

In summary, H1a was not supported (no significant immersion difference for sonified vs. silent scenes); H2a received partial support (Hybrid exceeded J and L on immersion); H2b and H2c were not supported (no EEG or workload advantage); H2d was failed to be rejected under current sample (Conceptual Structure based sonification was clearly preferred). The small sample ($n = 10$) limits statistical power; future work should target larger n .

6. Conclusion

Sonification was treated within a musicolinguistic framework as a Conceptual Structure (phonetic + syntactic + semantic) and evaluated comparatively in a real-time *E. coli* simulation. A five-scene design (J/K/L/M/N) was tested while varying only the sound-data mapping logic; immersion/engagement (IEQ-SF), mental workload (NASA-TLX), momentary attention/concentration (EEG), and preference were measured. Findings indicated that H1a (sonified–silent immersion difference) was not statistically confirmed. However, a significant scene effect emerged, and the Hybrid (M) condition outperformed J (Phonetic) and L (Syntactic) on immersion. This also can be interpreted as Semantic (K) means are the closest to the hybrid approach since it contains phonetics and syntax in essence. No significant advantages were observed for EEG concentration or workload, whereas preference results showed a clear dominance of Hybrid.

These outcomes suggest that, when designed as a multilayer conceptual knowledge protocol rather than a purely aesthetic sequencing, sonification is likely to strengthen user experience on the immersion dimension. Joint operation of phonetic (formant), syntactic (tetrachord/melody), and semantic (cadence) layers appears to render the temporal organisation of sound more coherent and traceable for participants. By contrast, no reduction in workload or increase in EEG-based attention was established—an interpretation consistent with the small sample size ($n = 10$), power loss under multiple comparisons, and the short-window of EEG estimation.

Methodologically, the unified JSON logging, artefact veto policies, and person-specific EEG baselines enhanced traceability and procedural consistency. The study thus offers both an experimental template and a set of design principles for conceptual-structure sonification (layer separation and recombination, single-dimension variance control, counter-balanced scene order).

From an application standpoint, the clear preference for Hybrid supports the practical value of layer-bound sonification in interactive interfaces. Results point to the benefit of producing a “legible texture” in contexts such as education, discovery-oriented data exploration, and mixed-reality systems, beyond what isolated auditory cues provide.

Limitations include a short project window and a small sample; accordingly, results should be regarded as indicative, however, not as evidence, with effect sizes reported for planning and replication. Future work should expand the cohort, increase EEG channel count, test cross-cultural perceptual differences, and model causal links among layers as a one-way production chain (*phonetic* → *syntactic* → *semantic*). Additional directions include enrichment of the Hybrid components layer-wise to isolate contributions and exploration of alternative semantic frameworks (e.g., modulation plans, discourse-level cadential schemes, electro-acoustic level sonification, etc.).

In summary, the evidence supports Hybrid (Conceptual Structure) sonification as a means to elevate immersion and to lead user preference. Although advantages in workload and EEG based concentration level were not observed, this design offers a structural benefit for interactive information transfer. With larger samples and enriched measurement protocols, this framework can consolidate into a replicable and extensible set of design principles for real-time data-to-sound interfaces.

7. Discussion

This study directly aligns with current theoretical discussions that examine the structural similarities between music and language at the formal and theoretical level, rather than analogical level. This approach, known in the literature as Identity Thesis, argues that syntax-semantics components in language can be compared to the interpretive counterparts of tonal/harmonic structures in music, and both fields can rely on similar formal processors [3]. Accordingly, this study examines the phonetic aspects of musical sound and tests them with a concrete application, and suggests that the results can also provide new discussion grounds for linguistics. The tetrachord-based syntactic sonification used in this study was selected for auralisation of abstract structures. Tetrachord sets (e.g., 4-17, 4-18, 4-24) are the basic organisational units in Schoenberg's music [32].

In the other hand, testing such formal parallels in practice also reveals certain new questions. Discovering the connection between musicolinguistic based sonification and human perception would not be enough; human related limits of this conceptual mapping should also be researched. Cross cultural perceptual differences are not identified, yet, it is best to be tested again after the sample size is expanded. This experience examined only one possibility of each sonification method, the theory suggests that each method can further be assessed. Due to the nature of the experiment design, all methods were considered as independent cases including the hybrid. It serves as an evidence-based pilot for establishing a sonification grammar based on the principle: Phonetic Form + Logical Form (Syntax) + Semantic Form = Grammar = Conceptual Structures = Conceptual Knowledge. This study is an attempt to move the concept of sonification beyond being regarded solely as the production of technical sound signals or solely as an aesthetic compositional practice.

7.1. The Experimental Design

The design is fully within-subjects, the same participant experiences all scenes; therefore, the main tool is RM-ANOVA. When sphericity was violated (Audibility), Greenhouse–Geisser was reported. For “sound vs control” comparisons, paired t-test was chosen, since measures from the same participant are compared (manipulation check). When measures were not normal (EEG), parametric was not insisted, Friedman was used. For categorical relations χ^2 was applied (independence and GOF). Since WCM is ordinal, both ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis were given; in small samples reporting parallel results gives more confidence. Shortly: for each variable the simplest test according to measurement level and assumptions was selected; instead of over–modeling, a readable and reproducible analysis path was preferred.

The immersion manipulation check (sonified vs. silent) did not reach significance; nevertheless, RM-ANOVA indicated a scene effect and M outperformed J and L. In IEQ-SF, the finding $M > J, L$ is aligned with the methodological expectation; in TLX and EEG the lack of significant difference points to two things: (i) small n and Bonferroni correction lowering the power, (ii) Hybrid more likely increases immersive structure than reduces load. In preferences, M leading with 80% is the most practical outcome in application terms: users want Hybrid. Country and exposure effects did not appear; if sample expands, culture–dependent semantic mappings should be tested.

As anticipated under H1a, sound scenes yielded a higher mean immersion score than the silent control; however, the difference did not reach statistical significance given the small sample. This outcome does not invalidate the manipulation, rather, it indicates a need for replication with greater power.

7.2. Directions for Future Design

First, findings indicate that immersion may increase when sonification is built as a conceptual structure. This effect is not confined to the specific musico-semantic devices used here; it can be amplified by introducing alternative phonetic, syntactic, and semantic tools. In the present design, each scenario was treated independently, and the Hybrid condition was realised by stacking those layers in parallel. A more organic pathway is to let layers generate one another—interlocked rather than merely co-present.

Second, a hierarchical, musicolinguistic chain in this case suggests itself: first, “phonemes” are formed at the phonetic level; next, those units are arranged by rule into structured sequences (syntax); finally, the sequences are embedded in a semantic context. In this way, a conceptual structure emerges from internal dependency rather than post-hoc layering. Concretely, instead of emitting isolated vowel tokens or fixed cadence templates, phonetic outputs can be grouped as arrays into “lexical phonemes” (e.g., “aea”, “ioe”), organised into melodic–syntactic fabrics, and only then situated within cadential or tonal–semantic frames. The result is a sonification grammar that feels coherent and meaningful rather than collaged.

Third, historical practice offers usable blueprints. The 15th-century “French Faux-bourdon” technique provides an early instance of tightly bound horizontal (syntactic) and vertical (harmonic/semantic) organisation: voices proceed in rule-governed intervallic relations within a given mode (pitch-set), producing built-in cadential closure [35]. Such procedures naturally fuse phonetic material, syntactic ordering, and semantic function into a single body—an instructive precedent for conceptual-structure sonification.

Fourth, a route involves “word painting,” understood in music as the deliberate mirroring of textual meaning through musical gestures (e.g., adding a chord tone on “improve,” thinning texture or inserting a rest on “silence”). Standard references describe this as mapping sense to sound; the same principle can be operationalised in data sonification as micro-level semantic coupling that is both perceptible and testable [36].

Then, the toolset for phonetic, syntactic, and semantic mapping is not limited to the examples above. The present study simplified conditions to four genomic parameters; nevertheless, a broader musicolinguistic repertoire is available for future designs: prosody and accent systems, rhythmic hierarchies and meter, articulatory envelopes, modal/tonal shifts and modulations, and discourse-level cadential plans. Pursuing these directions would shift the design axis from “stacking features” to “constructing grammars,” thereby strengthening ecological validity and deepening experiential coherence.

Furthermore, a recent study on spatial cadence perception shows that the concept of cadence is not limited to tonal harmony but can also create a sense of closure in spatial audio trajectories, and this effect is shown to be strengthened in listeners familiar with electro-acoustic music [33]. Also, cadences have broader semantic functions in film music, for example sub-tonic Half Cadence use in Western or John Williams’ awe-inspiring chromatic modulations have also been discussed [34]. In this sense, musicolinguistic should not be seen as a research field related to Western Classical Music only and musicolinguistic approach in data sonification can be assessed using different types of cadential effects, or other semantic approaches.

Finally, in further applications, more complex relations between these three levels can be created: while phonetic form defines wave forms and formant areas, the syntactic structure determines the spatial organisation of these elements, and the semantic level identifies the perceptual or cognitive meaning of it all.

7.3. Validity of EEG Tools

BrainFlow is a backbone that makes the EEG data flow uninterrupted. The Auditory Attention Decoding (AAD) article in Scientific Reports (2023) is a typical case [37]: Cyton (+Daisy) is used, EEG sampled at 125 Hz and streamed to the laptop through BrainFlow continuously. This is direct evidence of validity of BrainFlow, written explicitly inside a peer-reviewed experiment.

The second axis comes from Kremenska and Lekova [38]. More than 20 OpenBCI nodes for Node-RED are introduced, and the whole integration is declared built on BrainFlow’s unified acquisition API. Here the focus shifts from pure academic validity to IoT/edge integration. BrainFlow = not only lab-internal but also a reusable kernel in rapid prototyping and IoT scenarios. The “low-code flow” concept makes EEG data operational in Node-RED in minutes.

The BrainFlow citations page [31] also supports this three-fold picture: peer-reviewed validation (Scientific Reports), real-time hyperscanning (Frontiers / Methods), and ecosystem expansion (Node-RED / IoT).

In conclusion, BrainFlow is valid (explicitly reported in peer-reviewed method), modern (multi-device real-time processing + preprocessing), and scalable (Node-RED IoT nodes). These three evidence lines confirm that the library is academically and scientifically usable. However, it must be noted that the headset used in the study is a BrainBit device, which is only 4-channel, so the results are not conclusive proof, yet, supportive evidence.

7.4. Validity of The Simulation

The design of the simulation was not developed from scratch during the dissertation period; rather, it builds on an earlier prototype started to be developed by the author approximately two years prior (September 2023). The rationale was to capitalise on an already functional simulation pipeline, refine it to meet the reproducibility and experimental control standards required for this study, and thus enable a timely transition into empirical testing.

Additionally, the purpose of keeping the simulation this detailed is not to sonify every biological subprocess one by one, but to present the user with the most realistic evolutionary experience possible. This approach was chosen to increase the ecological validity of the experimental context. In the sonification, only four genomic parameters (optimal temperature, pH, UV resistance, and toxin resistance) were used to sonify; however, by positioning these parameters within a broader network of biological processes, the intention is to make the experience feel more natural to participants and to support the reliability of the resulting findings.

chemotaxis mechanism

E. coli’s response to chemical gradients is classically described as a run–tumble strategy. Cells make temporal comparisons of their environment and convert those comparisons into a biased random walk: runs become longer in the preferred direction of the gradient, while tumbles reorient the cell when evidence is weak or unfavourable [39]. In the simulation, this maps directly to the agent state machine and genome-tuned rates: $EColiAgent.State \in \{Run, Tumble\}$, with behaviour implemented by `Run()`, `StartTumble()`, and `Tumble()`. The bias is governed by `genome.baseTumbleRate`, `genome.tumbleDuration`, and `genome.runSpeedFactor`.

A key point in the biology is that chemotaxis requires temporal comparison—the cell must sense the present and retain a short memory of the recent past [39]. It is modelled that explicitly via `chemotaxisMemoryLength`, a rolling `concMemory` buffer, and decision parameters `tumbleSlopeSensitivity` and `gradientTolerance`.

The tumble rate has been defined as $v = v_0 \cdot C(X, l)$, with the function C monotonic increasing and normalised so that $C(0) = 1$. Experimental tracking yielded for *E. coli* the values $v_0 = 0.22 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\tau = 19 \text{ s}$, and $\lambda = 1.62$. In plain terms, this means that a bacterium like *E. coli* typically changes its swimming direction about once every 4–5 seconds, but this frequency is adjusted depending on the surrounding

chemical signals. The parameter τ indicates that the cell “remembers” changes in its environment over roughly 20 seconds, and λ reflects how strongly it reacts to those changes [40]. In the simulation, this basal tumble rate is represented by the parameter `genome.baseTumbleRate` and `memory`.

the use of biological noise

In the mathematical formalisation of run and tumble behaviours, a white noise term is included, with δ -correlation [40]. In the simulation, this element is represented by the parameter `decisionNoise`, which perturbs sensor precision and introduces randomness into behavioural trajectories.

Flow fields were not explicitly simulated; instead their net effect with `decisionNoise` and broadened `tumbleAngleRange` were proxied. The relative importance of steric vs hydrodynamic alignment remains unresolved [41]. In the model, this uncertainty is left tuneable and testable via parametric variation (e.g., `generalMutationRate`, `decisionNoise`). Crucially, rotational Brownian motion randomises heading during temporal comparisons, degrading chemotactic sensing [41]. The degradation is modelled with `decisionNoise`.

contact-driven events in the simulation

Multiple transfer and pairing mechanisms share a common implementation pattern. A spawned carrier or projection attempts contact, a collision event triggers a match/eligibility check, and a state transition unlocks transfer or stabilisation. This *contact* \rightarrow *check* \rightarrow *commit* sequence underlies phage-like transduction[42] (via `OnTriggerEnter()`-style callbacks).

mechanisms of high density & biofilms

At high cell densities, swimming bacteria exhibit collective motion patterns that self-organise through physical interactions [41]. In the simulation, this phenomenon is captured via `isQuorumActive`, the `UpdateSocialBehaviours()` routine, and density threshold parameters. The nutrient gradients generated by `EnvironmentManager` are kept independent of agent density.

7.5. Overall Reliability

Reliability was addressed in multiple layers. Consistency of the experimental manipulation was verified through an auditory exposure check; the superiority of the sonified condition over silent conditions was demonstrated with a paired t-test at a large-effect level ($t(9)=11.53$, $p<.001$, $d=3.65$). EEG data reliability was supported by a standard artefact-reduction pipeline (de-trend, 1–45 Hz band-pass filter, wavelet denoising) and z-scoring against a person-specific 30-second baseline. Non-overlapping 5-second windows were used, and windows exceeding predefined thresholds were excluded under a veto policy.

Procedural reliability was reinforced by a fixed synthesis chain across all scenes, counterbalanced scene orders, a stable cell-selection cadence, and timestamped records written to a single JSON log. Statistical reliability involved formal assumption checks; repeated-measures ANOVA was reported when sphericity held, and non-parametric alternative — Friedman — were applied when normality was violated. Given the small sample, effect sizes and confidence intervals were reported systematically.

The limited channel count of the BrainBit EEG device [43] was noted; accordingly, EEG concentration level results were interpreted as exploratory. All raw statistical outputs and session logs are provided in the appendices to ensure traceability and reproducibility.

7.6. Power

The sample size was limited to ($n = 10$), due to a three-month window from iterations, experimental design to reporting. As a result, statistical power may be humble, and the reported effects should be considered as provisional predictions pending approval with larger powered groups. Effect sizes are presented to inform future experiments and to support confirmation in expanded samples.

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APPENDICIES

Figure 9. Survey UI's

Figure 10. Survey UI's

Figure 11. Survey UI's

Figure 12. Survey UI's

Figure 13. Survey UI's

Figure 14. Survey UI's

Figure 14. Survey UI's

Figure 15. Survey UI's

Figure 24. Survey UI's

Figure 25. Resting Lobby

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